

1) DATSET1

a) number of missing nodes = 1

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.486	0.284	0.359	0.717	0.39
GraphRNN	0.244	0.21	0.225	0.645	0.465
DMNP-S	0.544	0.981	0.7	0.898	0.196
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.768	0.483	0.593	0.868	0.378
GraphRNN	0.212	0.13	0.161	0.842	0.643
DMNP-S	0.797	0.992	0.884	0.961	0.074
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.109	0.006	0.011	0.632	0.558
GraphRNN	0.146	0.021	0.037	0.643	0.557
DMNP-S	0.656	0.776	0.711	0.832	0.204
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.224	0.131	0.165	0.551	0.184
GraphRNN	0.184	0.131	0.153	0.551	0.175
DMNP-S	0.222	0.832	0.351	0.838	0.342
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.399	0.272	0.324	0.627	0.224
GraphRNN	0.276	0.194	0.228	0.561	0.188
DMNP-S	0.335	0.932	0.493	0.912	0.254

b) number of missing nodes = 2

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.573	0.303	0.397	0.699	0.392
GraphRNN	0.51	0.196	0.283	0.636	0.468
DMNP-M	0.544	0.981	0.7	0.705	0.421
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.788	0.42	0.548	0.859	0.43
GraphRNN	0.598	0.115	0.193	0.83	0.652
DMNP-M	0.797	0.991	0.883	0.842	0.185
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.205	0.008	0.015	0.606	0.558
GraphRNN	0.315	0.02	0.038	0.611	0.557
DMNP-M	0.66	0.8	0.723	0.812	0.22
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.207	0.121	0.153	0.546	0.208
GraphRNN	0.198	0.11	0.141	0.554	0.195
DMNP-M	0.237	0.611	0.341	0.653	0.419
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.364	0.24	0.289	0.607	0.265
GraphRNN	0.269	0.17	0.209	0.568	0.226
DMNP-M	0.34	0.776	0.473	0.699	0.436

c) number of missing nodes = 3

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.599	0.302	0.402	0.699	0.408
GraphRNN	0.529	0.183	0.272	0.64	0.477
DMNP-M	0.54	0.985	0.698	0.682	0.425
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.808	0.419	0.552	0.858	0.439
GraphRNN	0.756	0.121	0.208	0.835	0.654
DMNP-M	0.794	0.995	0.883	0.835	0.189
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.231	0.007	0.013	0.597	0.561
GraphRNN	0.348	0.021	0.039	0.6	0.556
DMNP-M	0.648	0.815	0.722	0.796	0.238
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.19	0.118	0.145	0.542	0.221
GraphRNN	0.177	0.101	0.129	0.539	0.211
DMNP-M	0.217	0.519	0.306	0.613	0.385
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.332	0.221	0.266	0.595	0.276
GraphRNN	0.25	0.157	0.193	0.554	0.244
DMNP-M	0.29	0.651	0.401	0.639	0.417

d) number of missing nodes = 4

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.605	0.324	0.422	0.701	0.402
GraphRNN	0.539	0.172	0.261	0.645	0.484
DMNP-M	0.541	0.984	0.698	0.66	0.424
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.813	0.406	0.541	0.861	0.457
GraphRNN	0.75	0.103	0.181	0.843	0.671
DMNP-M	0.796	0.993	0.884	0.829	0.187
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.264	0.006	0.012	0.596	0.562
GraphRNN	0.403	0.022	0.041	0.604	0.558
DMNP-M	0.647	0.828	0.726	0.789	0.244
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.192	0.12	0.148	0.544	0.224
GraphRNN	0.175	0.101	0.128	0.54	0.216
DMNP-M	0.205	0.43	0.278	0.597	0.356
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.281	0.183	0.222	0.575	0.264
GraphRNN	0.228	0.154	0.184	0.544	0.253
DMNP-M	0.271	0.6	0.373	0.606	0.416

e) number of missing nodes = 5

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.607	0.326	0.424	0.703	0.405
GraphRNN	0.55	0.161	0.25	0.654	0.491
DMNP-M	0.542	0.984	0.699	0.659	0.424
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.773	0.329	0.462	0.865	0.516
GraphRNN	0.71	0.086	0.154	0.85	0.689
DMNP-M	0.794	0.988	0.881	0.827	0.186
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.279	0.006	0.01	0.598	0.564
GraphRNN	0.455	0.023	0.043	0.605	0.558
DMNP-M	0.649	0.81	0.721	0.785	0.233
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.179	0.114	0.139	0.536	0.227
GraphRNN	0.167	0.093	0.119	0.532	0.216
DMNP-M	0.202	0.41	0.271	0.577	0.354
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.262	0.163	0.201	0.561	0.264
GraphRNN	0.22	0.148	0.177	0.54	0.251
DMNP-M	0.24	0.545	0.333	0.586	0.409

f) number of missing nodes = 6

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.615	0.331	0.43	0.704	0.41
GraphRNN	0.556	0.151	0.238	0.657	0.498
DMNP-M	0.54	0.986	0.698	0.669	0.425
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.734	0.249	0.371	0.868	0.582
GraphRNN	0.706	0.076	0.138	0.858	0.702
DMNP-M	0.718	0.998	0.835	0.774	0.261
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.3	0.006	0.011	0.599	0.567
GraphRNN	0.498	0.024	0.045	0.608	0.561
DMNP-M	0.643	0.803	0.715	0.782	0.233
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.174	0.11	0.135	0.534	0.222
GraphRNN	0.164	0.094	0.12	0.532	0.211
DMNP-M	0.197	0.412	0.267	0.568	0.361
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.238	0.15	0.184	0.553	0.252
GraphRNN	0.236	0.152	0.185	0.549	0.267
DMNP-M	0.24	0.519	0.328	0.581	0.393

2) DATSET2

a) number of missing nodes = 1

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.027	0.016	0.02	0.687	0.51
GraphRNN	0.007	0.006	0.007	0.66	0.525
DeepGMG	0.234	0.256	0.244	0.537	0.472
DMNP-S	0.638	0.792	0.707	0.739	0.329
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.87	0.733
GraphRNN	0.008	0.007	0.008	0.872	0.733
DeepGMG	0.454	0.342	0.391	0.625	0.514
DMNP-S	0.84	0.977	0.903	0.911	0.114
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.26	0.194	0.222	0.587	0.256
GraphRNN	0.231	0.174	0.199	0.584	0.253
DeepGMG	0.564	0.451	0.501	0.672	0.172
DMNP-S	0.396	0.842	0.539	0.838	0.311
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.275	0.117	0.164	0.673	0.356
GraphRNN	0.425	0.391	0.407	0.678	0.256
DeepGMG	0.494	0.386	0.433	0.622	0.302
DMNP-S	0.527	0.911	0.668	0.883	0.268

b) number of missing nodes = 2

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.263	0.073	0.114	0.669	0.505
GraphRNN	0.01	0.007	0.008	0.644	0.534
DeepGMG	0.258	0.157	0.195	0.510	0.495
DMNP-M	0.76	0.63	0.689	0.703	0.332
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.025	0.005	0.008	0.861	0.739
GraphRNN	0.29	0.059	0.099	0.856	0.702
DeepGMG	0.523	0.281	0.269	0.558	0.607
DMNP-M	0.833	0.95	0.888	0.858	0.15
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.324	0.182	0.233	0.573	0.287
GraphRNN	0.336	0.159	0.216	0.582	0.29
DeepGMG	0.626	0.321	0.425	0.622	0.182
DMNP-M	0.37	0.645	0.47	0.671	0.393
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.505	0.272	0.353	0.657	0.332
GraphRNN	0.556	0.332	0.416	0.663	0.33
DeepGMG	0.505	0.235	0.321	0.564	0.340
DMNP-M	0.521	0.767	0.621	0.72	0.342

c) number of missing nodes = 3

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.436	0.121	0.19	0.66	0.494
GraphRNN	0.013	0.008	0.01	0.64	0.54
DeepGMG	0.327	0.131	0.167	0.508	0.499
DMNP-M	0.616	0.844	0.712	0.718	0.352
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.015	0.003	0.005	0.864	0.748
GraphRNN	0.767	0.106	0.186	0.858	0.679
DeepGMG	0.559	0.120	0.197	0.537	0.642
DMNP-M	0.834	0.965	0.895	0.852	0.152
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.346	0.203	0.256	0.568	0.319
GraphRNN	0.307	0.154	0.205	0.56	0.315
DeepGMG	0.653	0.257	0.368	0.594	0.196
DMNP-M	0.353	0.566	0.435	0.624	0.393
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.523	0.308	0.388	0.644	0.358
GraphRNN	0.483	0.339	0.399	0.643	0.379
DeepGMG	0.579	0.174	0.267	0.545	0.368
DMNP-M	0.49	0.732	0.587	0.67	0.361

d) number of missing nodes = 4

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.547	0.166	0.255	0.669	0.485
GraphRNN	0.016	0.008	0.01	0.641	0.548
DeepGMG	0.372	0.085	0.138	0.506	0.506
DMNP-M	0.587	0.925	0.718	0.683	0.374
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.012	0.003	0.004	0.87	0.758
GraphRNN	0.765	0.087	0.156	0.867	0.701
DeepGMG	0.653	0.092	0.162	0.532	0.663
DMNP-M	0.834	0.984	0.903	0.854	0.15
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.324	0.205	0.251	0.563	0.336
GraphRNN	0.308	0.176	0.224	0.564	0.33
DeepGMG	0.643	0.213	0.320	0.572	0.210
DMNP-M	0.326	0.493	0.392	0.608	0.395
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.502	0.327	0.396	0.63	0.387
GraphRNN	0.476	0.387	0.427	0.628	0.4
DeepGMG	0.520	0.128	0.205	0.527	0.381
DMNP-M	0.455	0.634	0.53	0.623	0.387

e) number of missing nodes = 5

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.618	0.195	0.296	0.677	0.472
GraphRNN	0.019	0.008	0.011	0.649	0.556
DeepGMG	0.425	0.069	0.118	0.510	0.507
DMNP-M	0.576	0.713	0.637	0.668	0.358
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.01	0.002	0.004	0.879	0.767
GraphRNN	0.583	0.056	0.102	0.878	0.733
DeepGMG	0.737	0.071	0.129	0.527	0.682
DMNP-M	0.834	0.991	0.906	0.852	0.149
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.301	0.204	0.243	0.555	0.349
GraphRNN	0.311	0.184	0.231	0.556	0.337
DeepGMG	0.649	0.169	0.268	0.553	0.225
DMNP-M	0.309	0.497	0.381	0.588	0.413
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.508	0.352	0.416	0.628	0.403
GraphRNN	0.426	0.351	0.385	0.622	0.419
DeepGMG	0.572	0.116	0.193	0.525	0.359
DMNP-M	0.402	0.542	0.461	0.595	0.39

f) number of missing nodes = 6

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.675	0.215	0.326	0.688	0.476
GraphRNN	0.02	0.008	0.012	0.657	0.564
DeepGMG	0.521	0.107	0.102	0.511	0.514
DMNP-M	0.544	0.827	0.657	0.665	0.378
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.007	0.002	0.003	0.882	0.771
GraphRNN	0.444	0.039	0.072	0.884	0.752
DeepGMG	0.798	0.048	0.091	0.518	0.700
DMNP-M	0.795	0.979	0.877	0.813	0.189
ENZYMES DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.322	0.216	0.258	0.561	0.352
GraphRNN	0.32	0.193	0.241	0.566	0.342
DeepGMG	0.624	0.146	0.237	0.543	0.232
DMNP-M	0.303	0.434	0.357	0.565	0.397
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.479	0.353	0.406	0.620	0.401
GraphRNN	0.372	0.308	0.337	0.606	0.42
DeepGMG	0.5909	0.106	0.180	0.521	0.3305
DMNP-M	0.37	0.5308	0.4309	0.583	0.424

3) DATSET3

a) number of missing nodes = 1

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.283	0.122	0.17	0.621	0.403
GraphRNN	0.189	0.129	0.154	0.556	0.431
KronEM	0.480	0.663	0.557	0.556	0.470
DMNP-S	0.487	1.0	0.655	0.94	0.122
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.644	0.308	0.416	0.925	0.573
GraphRNN	0.747	0.704	0.725	0.896	0.253
KronEM	0.763	0.692	0.726	0.617	0.360
DMNP-S	0.874	1.0	0.932	0.98	0.041
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.556	0.297	0.387	0.729	0.333
GraphRNN	0.48	0.33	0.391	0.694	0.337
KronEM	0.537	0.501	0.518	0.573	0.465
DMNP-S	0.56	0.999	0.718	0.958	0.123
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.327	0.201	0.249	0.6	0.197
GraphRNN	0.254	0.154	0.192	0.574	0.203
KronEM	0.212	0.384	0.273	0.520	0.373
DMNP-S	0.235	0.858	0.369	0.853	0.233

b) number of missing nodes = 2

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.345	0.126	0.184	0.597	0.409
GraphRNN	0.286	0.106	0.154	0.533	0.416
KronEM	0.453	0.643	0.531	0.532	0.487
DMNP-M	0.464	1.0	0.634	0.634	0.502
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.812	0.348	0.487	0.918	0.544
GraphRNN	0.835	0.615	0.708	0.898	0.327
KronEM	0.775	0.695	0.733	0.594	0.354
DMNP-M	0.866	1.0	0.928	0.892	0.12
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.596	0.292	0.392	0.72	0.344
GraphRNN	0.538	0.305	0.389	0.676	0.363
KronEM	0.503	0.472	0.487	0.551	0.478
DMNP-M	0.554	0.999	0.712	0.782	0.433
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.312	0.168	0.219	0.581	0.233
GraphRNN	0.324	0.164	0.217	0.577	0.239
KronEM	0.236	0.390	0.294	0.520	0.362
DMNP-M	0.226	0.804	0.353	0.704	0.554

c) number of missing nodes = 3

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.378	0.124	0.187	0.582	0.417
GraphRNN	0.358	0.115	0.174	0.527	0.410
KronEM	0.454	0.635	0.529	0.532	0.485
DMNP-M	0.464	1.0	0.634	0.618	0.502
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.795	0.329	0.465	0.914	0.553
GraphRNN	0.882	0.586	0.704	0.906	0.356
KronEM	0.772	0.704	0.736	0.590	0.337
DMNP-M	0.87	0.971	0.918	0.89	0.144
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.602	0.285	0.387	0.717	0.356
GraphRNN	0.559	0.287	0.379	0.678	0.374
KronEM	0.539	0.471	0.503	0.569	0.471
DMNP-M	0.551	0.999	0.71	0.788	0.436
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.243	0.133	0.172	0.563	0.250
GraphRNN	0.269	0.151	0.193	0.561	0.258
KronEM	0.217	0.352	0.269	0.506	0.371
DMNP-M	0.239	0.781	0.366	0.673	0.511

d) number of missing nodes = 4

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.432	0.147	0.22	0.58	0.411
GraphRNN	0.349	0.118	0.177	0.523	0.411
KronEM	0.466	0.632	0.537	0.536	0.475
DMNP-M	0.477	1.0	0.645	0.602	0.491
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.744	0.178	0.287	0.913	0.665
GraphRNN	0.899	0.527	0.665	0.915	0.401
KronEM	0.759	0.713	0.735	0.573	0.325
DMNP-M	0.868	1.0	0.929	0.891	0.119
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.601	0.273	0.375	0.717	0.372
GraphRNN	0.561	0.268	0.363	0.676	0.391
KronEM	0.528	0.483	0.504	0.565	0.474
DMNP-M	0.554	0.999	0.713	0.772	0.433
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.252	0.124	0.166	0.557	0.245
GraphRNN	0.243	0.146	0.182	0.558	0.25
KronEM	0.218	0.347	0.267	0.514	0.375
DMNP-M	0.238	0.711	0.357	0.626	0.505

e) number of missing nodes = 5

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.453	0.163	0.24	0.572	0.409
GraphRNN	0.354	0.124	0.183	0.521	0.415
KronEM	0.439	0.598	0.507	0.502	0.510
DMNP-M	0.477	1.0	0.646	0.603	0.49
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.805	0.178	0.291	0.924	0.673
GraphRNN	0.897	0.514	0.654	0.917	0.418
KronEM	0.743	0.690	0.715	0.568	0.372
DMNP-M	0.865	1.0	0.928	0.883	0.121
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.605	0.244	0.348	0.719	0.401
GraphRNN	0.57	0.248	0.345	0.675	0.414
KronEM	0.533	0.470	0.499	0.560	0.478
DMNP-M	0.547	0.999	0.707	0.770	0.44
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.213	0.114	0.148	0.553	0.245
GraphRNN	0.232	0.149	0.181	0.553	0.243
KronEM	0.219	0.322	0.261	0.513	0.387
DMNP-M	0.221	0.708	0.337	0.575	0.513

f) number of missing nodes = 6

	Precision	Recall	F1	AUC-ROC	MAE
IMDB-BINARY DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.461	0.191	0.27	0.576	0.411
GraphRNN	0.349	0.125	0.184	0.522	0.416
KronEM	0.464	0.611	0.528	0.522	0.487
DMNP-M	0.469	1.0	0.638	0.606	0.498
IMDB-MULTI DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.844	0.185	0.304	0.920	0.66
GraphRNN	0.898	0.443	0.593	0.915	0.476
KronEM	0.699	0.687	0.692	0.547	0.384
DMNP-M	0.868	1.0	0.929	0.887	0.119
COLLAB DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.611	0.224	0.328	0.72	0.427
GraphRNN	0.571	0.222	0.319	0.678	0.443
KronEM	0.535	0.474	0.503	0.561	0.472
DMNP-M	0.552	0.998	0.711	0.755	0.435
PROTEINS DATASET					
GraphRNN-S	0.267	0.147	0.19	0.558	0.265
GraphRNN	0.257	0.165	0.201	0.557	0.262
KronEM	0.214	0.314	0.255	0.511	0.392
DMNP-M	0.233	0.581	0.333	0.580	0.415